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Political Parties as Subject of Public-Administrative Relations in Political Governance System

*Oleksii Kriukov*¹

¹ National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine, Kharkiv

Abstract. The paper considers political parties as political governance subject. The mechanisms of political parties' functioning under the parliamentary democracy conditions are analyzed. The role of electoral systems within the system of public administration is emphasized. Keywords: political parties, parliamentary democracy, political governance, electoral systems.

Introduction

It is obvious, in our opinion, that democracy as a social phenomenon and a subject of public-administrative relations cannot exist without political parties. For parliamentary democracy is, first and foremost, a party democracy. Without political parties, democracy is incapable. The presence in society of various political parties reflects the indisputable fact that people are inherently different and have different interests. Under parliamentary representative democracy, political parties are carriers of a variety of ideas and approaches, political pluralism. In modern political governance systems, parties serve to represent the interests of citizens. It is well known that political parties tend to fight not for stand-alone public interests, but for the societies' will, which distinguishes them from other political institutions (e.g., interest groups). However, when a party starts claiming the right to decide what is to benefit all citizens, or when it claims to have a monopoly on truth or patriotism, this, as history has shown, leads to fatal social consequences. Such understanding of political parties' essence poses a threat to democracy [1, c. 2-3]]. The foregoing testifies to the fact that parties are an most important instrument of political governance of society and the state.

Theory of the matter

Quite a large number of publications have been devoted to the problem of the role and place of parties in the system of political government. In the first place, the works by the authors who are rightly recognized as classics in the field should be addressed, specifically those written by M. Weber, M. Ostrogorsky, R. Michels, M. Duverger, P. Bourdieu and some others. In the post-Soviet space, numerous authors also devoted their publications to

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the role of political parties in the government process, the most significant, in our opinion, being the works by such authors as G. Ashin, O. Kriukov, Ye. Okhotskiy, O. Radchenko, F. Rudich, A. Zotkin, and some other researchers.

At the same time, it should be mentioned that despite the fact that the problem has been thoroughly researched, the role of parties as part of the political and administrative elite within the system of political governance and public administration remains insufficiently explored.

Discussion of results

Based on the foregoing, the objective of this publication is defined as a scientific analysis of the role of political parties in public-administrative relations and in the system of political governance as a whole.

Despite the fact that under the conditions of a democratic society and democratic political organization political parties play a significant role in the political governance system, they should not be idealized.

In the absence of proper containment and counterbalancing mechanisms, and lack of public control over the parties' efforts to maximize their social influence, they may go too far. Democracy, as R. Michaels puts it, always tends to transform into oligarchy. The scientist writes that recognizing organization means an expression of a tendency for an oligarchy. In its essence, any organization (parties, trade unions, etc.) contains deeply rooted aristocratic features. An organizational machine that creates massive structures causes major changes in organized masses [2, c.30].

Candidates who are elected on a proportional basis, first and foremost, fight for being put on the party list, which is at the disposal of the party apparatus, not the voters. In fact, when choosing a party, a voter chooses its apparatus. Under the proportional system, as M. Duverger noted, the party becomes the only constituency [3, c.307].

M. Ostrogorskiy's warning that even under a parliamentary democracy it is not always possible to overcome the alienation of society from governance and state power must not be overlooked. The scientist showed how in the conditions of equal suffrage, the population could be kept away from political life and subject to manipulation on behalf of the party elite [4, c.23].

M. Weber points out that the development of universal suffrage leads to the transformation of parties from associations of prominent people into "party machines", the activity of which is governed by party bosses (the party elite). And this, in turn, results in a plebiscite democracy which he identifies with dictatorship that is based on the emotionality of the masses. Thus, according to Weber, a plebiscite dictator rises above the parliament, subjugating masses with the help of the "machine", parliamentarians only being his escort [5, c. 25].

These warnings of the classics of political party theory are particularly relevant to transitional societies which, without doubt, include most of post-Soviet states as well. It should not be forgotten that under certain social conditions political parties may assume a totalitarian nature, laying the basis for a totalitarian regime. The history of totalitarian parties – fascist and communist ones – provides ample evidence of this.

It is commonly known that political parties differ from other political associations in that they want to exercise political power and political control, which enables them to put into practice their perceptions of the proper state of society. In a parliamentary democracy, the

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only way to take power is to win elections. In such a case, the power will undoubtedly belong to those who clearly distinguish between the interests of the voters, are engaged in a task-oriented daily work with them, and do not rely solely on election technology or administrative resources.

As stated above, the role of political parties is especially important in the transformational periods. In the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, Asia, Africa, Latin America, the process of political modernization and democratization being inextricably linked to political parties' activities. However, both lack of experience in implementing democratic changes and political parties formation and operation, can put a heavy burden on the development of democracy. Unfortunately, parties and political elites do not always respond adequately to challenges of the transformation period.

It has been argued in scientific literature that modern political systems, considered to be democratic, are based on party leadership, that is, on the governance by a certain part of the party machine – the party elite, which, in turn, is part of the political elite.

The notion of democracy is linked to a process that guarantees the appearance of people who hold public functions due to the victory of a particular political party in general elections. It is also possible to imagine non-partisan elections; yet, in modern practice, a prerequisite for the democratic rule is a competitive party system.

Applying this analysis to the party system level, we should recognize the need to adhere to the additional conditions which facilitate stabilization of the negotiation process between political parties and are a major factor that shapes good political governance and public policy.

There are three types of political instruments in the system of political governance that influence or may influence a political party's activities, namely: a type of electoral system; the structure of parliament; and a type of political regime.

Electoral systems can create such interesting phenomena as over-presentation (when parties receive more seats than votes cast), and under-presentation (when parties receive fewer seats than votes cast).

Some scholars divide the electoral systems into weak and strong ones. The main criterion for this classification is the degree of the electoral system's influence on the voters. A weak electoral system does not apply special elements of increasing imbalance when fighting for deputy mandates, but a strong system does.

Strong systems apply manipulative influence to voters, as well as to the course and nature of inter-party rivalry, providing an opportunity to stabilize a stronger version of party leadership.

Firstly, a strong system restricts the voters' choice by pushing them to support a stronger political party in order to win inter-party competition (the leader of the last parliamentary elections in Ukraine of July 2019 – the presidential party 'Servant of the People' – can be an example). Thus, it is the fear of losing of a vote that becomes the main motive determining voters' sympathy.

Secondly, it does not encourage small parties to participate in inter-party struggle, since their chances to get to parliament are minimal.

Thirdly, strong electoral systems make it difficult to change the party system. Weak systems do not exclude the possibility of stabilizing the party leadership, however, as a rule, there appears a weaker version of it.

Thus, the immediate aim of a party is to assume certain public positions, while the long-term goal is to influence the content of state policy and political governance. Political

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parties, as state-political focal points, propose a specific coalition strategy or a catalog of political conditions and requirements that determine the framework of the inter-party relations. This applies primarily to multi-party systems, in which government cabinets are usually of a coalition nature.

Many of researchers studying democracies in Western Europe use a common thesis of a party leadership crisis. The first type of argument to confirm the existence of a party leadership crisis can be called electoral. This refers to re-designing the mutual relations established between the parties and the electorate. The transformation of a party model means that the elected party ceases to perform its functions effectively, in particular the mobilization one. In that case, the party's links with its electorate weaken, the electorate becoming less structured and less consistent in their political sympathies. Obviously, this affects the stability of the state power.

The central argument is a change in voter loyalty. A decreased loyalty should signal the crisis of stable parties. There are doubts as to whether the changeability of electoral preferences proves the thesis of the party leadership crisis. The value of this index is growing, but not dramatically, especially for Western Europe where there are no strong anti-system parties.

Conclusion

A certain alternative to party leadership is exemplified by the direct democracy forms of Switzerland, which enable the society to exert a direct impact on decision-making, and the referendum model can at least theoretically recognize that a citizen is capable of shaping state policy.

In practice, however, it turns out that the referendum is only advisory in nature, public initiative being very rare. An extremely small number of laws are enacted in this way. It is the parliament, not the electorate, who approves most of legal decisions during voting. The existence of large coalitions in Switzerland is a way to eliminate the devastating effects of the elements of direct democracy within a centralized political system.

Therefore, the possibility of using these instruments provides premises that the parliamentary majority may be defeated during popular vote. To minimize this risk, a coalition is formed that embraces a wide range of political parties and interest groups. This is significant because the effectiveness of the consensus approval of decision-making depends on the degree of interest aggregation. Thus, today the question of the party leadership crisis is rather theoretical than practical [6, c.198, 203].

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